

**POREĐENJE VAGINALNE FLORE U KATEGORIJI NEGATIVNO NA INTRAEPITELNU LEZIJU I
MALIGNITET (NILM) SA VAGINALNOM FLOROM SA ATIPIJOM SKVAMOZNIH ČELIJA:
ANALIZA REZULTATA PAPA BRISA**

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**COMPARISON OF VAGINAL FLORA IN NEGATIVE FOR INTRAEPITHELIAL LESION AND
MALIGNANCY (NILM) CATEGORY WITH VAGINAL FLORA SHOWING SQUAMOUS CELL
ATYPIA: ANALYSIS OF PAP SMEAR RESULTS**

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Sažetak

Papa test je oslonac ginekološkog skrininga već više od 50 godina. U istraživanju sprovedenom u Zavodu za laboratorijsku dijagnostiku Biotest u Novom Sadu, analizirano je 24856 uzoraka Papa brisa u periodu od 2020. do 2023. godine. Rezultati su pokazali da je 99,8% uzoraka bilo adekvatno za analizu. Vaginalna flora kategorije NILM dominirala je mešovitom bakterijskom florom (61%) i laktobacilima (28,7%), dok je u kategoriji sa atipičnim skvamoznim ćelijama primećen porast HPV-a (8,3%). Zaključak istraživanja potvrđuje da je Papa test efikasan, brz i neinvazivan skrining test za otkrivanje prekanceroznih i kanceroznih promena. Ovi rezultati naglašavaju važnost redovnog obavljanja Papa testova u prevenciji ginekoloških oboljenja.

Abstract

The Pap test has been the cornerstone of gynecological screening for over 50 years. In a study conducted at the Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics Biotest in Novi Sad, 24856 Pap smear samples were analyzed from 2020 to 2023. The results showed that 99.8% of the samples were adequate for analysis. Vaginal flora in the NILM category was predominantly mixed bacterial flora (61%) and *Lactobacillus spp.* (28.7%), while an increase in HPV (8.3%) was observed in the category with squamous cell atypia. The conclusion of the study confirms that the Pap test is an effective, rapid, and non-invasive screening test for detecting precancerous and cancerous changes. These results emphasize the importance of regular Pap testing in the prevention of gynecological diseases.

Ključne reči: Papa test; HPV; vaginalna flora.

Keywords: Pap test; HPV; vaginal flora.

1. Introduction

The normal vaginal microflora of women comprises around 50 species of microorganisms. Its role is to protect the mucous membrane from invasion by pathogenic microorganisms, primarily those causing urogenital infections and sexually transmitted diseases. The number and type of microorganisms vary according to the woman's age as well as the influence of various internal and external factors [1].

In healthy vaginal microflora, *Lactobacillus spp.* dominates; these are microaerophilic and facultatively anaerobic gram-positive bacteria [2].

The composition of the vaginal ecosystem is not static but changes over time and in response to endogenous and exogenous factors [3].

Changes occur during the menstrual cycle, pregnancy, use of oral contraceptives, frequent changes in sexual partners, and the use of antibiotics and other drugs that can affect the endocrine system [4].

Bacteria and fungi are the most commonly present microorganisms in cervical swabs, but they are not associated with abnormalities of the cervix, while HPV is less common but is associated with cervical abnormalities [5].

The possible relationship between bacterial vaginosis (BV) and cervical intraepithelial tissue lesions has been presumed since the 1970s [6].

2. Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at the Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics Biotest in Novi Sad. Data were obtained from the archive of cytological findings of female patients. The research was conducted from 2020 to 2023. A total of 24856 Pap smear samples were included in the study, with 46 Pap smears being inadequate samples and 24810 being adequate samples.

Smears were stained using the Papanicolaou method. Pap smear can detect bacterial, viral, fungal, and protozoan infections [7].

Lactobacillus is the main microorganism in the normal lower female genital tract. It is an aerobic gram-positive rod. Stained with the Papanicolaou method, it appears lightly basophilic, varies in length, and can be found on the surface of squamous cells as well as in the background of the smear.

Gardnerella vaginalis is a short rod, which can be Gram-negative or Gram-variable. Stained with the Papanicolaou method, it appears dark blue. This microorganism tends to accumulate on the surface of squamous cells, giving them a characteristic appearance called "clue cells".

The two most common pathogenic species in the fungal group are *Candida albicans* and *Torulopsis glabrata*. Like most fungi, these two species occur in two forms: pseudohyphae and conidia. Conidia are small, round or oval encapsulated structures, while pseudohyphae resemble long thin threads that are segmented and resemble bamboo poles.

Leptotrix is a form of *Lactobacillus*. It appears as elongated, diffusely distributed, fibrous, filamentous, cord-like structures.

Trichomonas vaginalis is grayish-green, round or elliptical, ranging in size from 8 to 12 μm . It has an ec-

centrically placed, light vesicular nucleus, the cytoplasm is eosinophilic with frequently present granules. Flagella are present only at one pole of the parasite, but only in well-preserved samples. Dense inflammatory infiltrate mainly composed of polymorphonuclear cells forms the background [8].

Cytological diagnosis was classified according to the Bethesda System (TBS). The Bethesda classification represents a modern classification of cytological changes in the PAP test, which has been used since 1988. [9].

The objectives of the Bethesda System (TBS) were to provide effective communication from the laboratory to the clinician; facilitate cytohistological correlation; facilitate epidemiological research, research on cervical disease pathology; and provide reproducible and reliable data for national statistical analyses and comparisons of international statistical analyses [9].

3. Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was to identify microorganisms present in Pap smears and to compare the difference between the presence of microorganisms in the NILM category and those present in the category with squamous cell atypia.

4. Results

A total of 24856 cytological analyses of Pap smears from the archive of the Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics Biotest were included in the study from 2020 to 2023.

The study included 24810 Pap smear samples, with 46 Pap smears being inadequate samples and 24810 being adequate samples.

In this study, a total of 24810 Pap smear samples were compared. In the NILM category, the distribution of microorganisms was as follows: mixed bacterial flora 61.00%, *Lactobacillus spp.* 28.70%, *Gardnerella vaginalis* 5.90%, *Candida spp.* 4.00%, *Leptotrix* 0.20%, *Trichomonas vaginalis* 0.20% (Graph 1).

Graph 1. Distribution of Microorganisms in the NILM Category.

The distribution of microorganisms in the category with squamous cell atypia is as follows: mixed bacterial flora 54.00%, *Lactobacillus spp.* 26.00%, *Gardnerella vaginalis* 7.60%, *Candida spp.* 3.60%, *Leptotrix* 0.30%, *Trichomonas vaginalis* 0.20%, HPV 8.30% (Graph 2).

Graph 2. Distribution of Microorganisms in the Category with Squamous Cell Atypia.

Comparing the vaginal flora of the NILM category and the vaginal flora of the category with squamous cell atypia, we obtained the following results (Graph 3).

Graph 3. Comparison of vaginal flora in the NILM category and the category with squamous cell atypia.

The results of the t-test ($p=0.84$) showed that there is no statistically significant difference between these two categories.

5. Discussion

The Pap test is a simple, cost-effective, and reliable screening test that has been used worldwide for over 50 years [9].

Genital infections are the most common reason women visit gynecologists, and sexually transmitted diseases have been on the rise in recent decades [10].

The discovery of HPV as the main etiological agent in cervical cancer and its precursors has revolutionized cervical screening and the role of cytology in the screening process [11].

Trichomonas vaginalis, the causative agent of trichomoniasis, is the most common curable sexually transmitted organism in the world. It parasitizes both men and women and in the initial stage is asymptomatic [12,13].

In this study of 24810 adequate Pap smear samples, the NILM category accounted for 96.4%, while the category with squamous cell atypia accounted for 3.6%. The findings of this study showed that *Trichomonas vaginalis* was present in 0.20%, *Candida spp.* in 3.60%, and HPV in 8.30%, while in the study conducted by Alvahaii et al., *Trichomonas vaginalis* was present in 0.40%, *Candida spp.* in 0.36%, and HPV in 1.7% [14]. Cytological characteristics of HPV infection include koilocytosis and neoplasia [15]. Several studies have shown that candida infection is more prevalent in Pap smears [16,17]. In this study, there was no HSV infection, while in the study conducted by Alvahaii et al., HSV infection was rare and present in 0.1%. Similar results of HSV infection were found in other studies as well [18,19].

6. CONCLUSION

The sample consisted of 24856 cytological analyses of Pap smears from the archive of the Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics Biotest during the period from 2020 to 2023.

The study included 24810 Pap smear samples, with 46 Pap smears being inadequate samples and 24810 being adequate samples.

In this study, a total of 24810 Pap smear samples were compared. In the NILM category, the distribution of microorganisms was as follows: mixed bacterial flora 61.00%, lactobacilli 28.70%, *Gardnerella vaginalis* 5.90%, *Candida spp.* 4.00%, *Leptotrix* 0.20%, *Trichomonas vaginalis* 0.20%.

The distribution of microorganisms in the category with squamous cell atypia was as follows: mixed bacterial flora 54.00%, lactobacilli 26.00%, *Gardnerella vaginalis* 7.60%, *Candida spp.* 3.60%, *Leptotrix* 0.30%, *Trichomonas vaginalis* 0.20%, HPV 8.30%.

The results of the t-test (p 0.84) showed that there is no statistically significant difference between these two categories.

This study was conducted on data collected at the Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics Biotest. In conclusion, our findings indicate that bacteria and fungi are the most commonly present microorganisms in cervical swabs, but they are not directly associated with cervical abnormalities, while HPV and HSV are less common but are associated with the occurrence of cervical abnormalities. These results emphasize the importance of regular Pap testing in the prevention of gynecological diseases.

References

1. Vaginitisi, Mahira Jahić, Tuzla 2014 godine, (39)
2. Lidbeck A, Nord CE, Clinical Infectious Diseases, "Lactobacilli and the normal human anaerobic microflora," 1993;16 S181-187
3. Priestley C, Jones B, Priestley CJ, Jones BM, Dhar J, Goodwin L, et al., "What is normal vaginal flora?," Genitourinary Medicine (1997) 73(3) 230
4. Ravel J, Gajer P, Abdo Z, Schneider GM, Koeing SSK, McCulle SL, et al., Proceedings of the National Academy of Science, "Vaginal microbiome of reproductive-age women," (2011) 108 Suppl. 1, 4680-4687
5. Evaluation of Microorganisms in Cervical Smears: A Single Institutional Experience Nasar Alwahaibi1, Mai Mohammed Alrubkhi2 Usha Rani Bai2; Asian Pac J Cancer Biol, 4 (1), 11-14
6. Lukic A, Canzio C, Patella A, Giovagnoli M, Cipriani P, Frega A, Moscarini. Determination of cervicovaginal microorganisms in women with abnormal cervical cytology: the role of *Ureaplasma urealyticum*. Anticancer Research. 2006;26(6c):4843-9.
7. Avwioro OG. Diagnosis of trichomoniasis in Pap smears; how effective is it. European Journal of Experimental Biology. 2011;1(1):10-3
8. Ljiljana Tadić Latitović, Citologija cervikalnog brisa, NoviSad, 2021 godine.
9. National Cancer Institute Workshop: The Bethesda System 2001.
10. The Bethesda System for Reporting Cervical Cytology: A Historical Perspective Subject Area: Pathology and Cell Biology Ritu Nayar; David C. Wilbur Acta Cytologica (2017) 61 (4-5): 359–372. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000477556>
11. Evolution of the Pap smear to cervical cancer screening today <https://www.eurocytology.eu/course/cervical-cytology-2/> Datum pregleda:10.06.2023
12. Schwebke, J. R.; Burgess, D. (2004). Clinical Microbiology Reviews 17 (4): 794–803
13. Soper, D (2004). American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology 190 (1): 281–90.
14. Alwahaibi, Nasar, et al. 2019, "Evaluation of Microorganisms in Cervical Smears: A Single Institutional Experience."
15. Trofatter KF. Diagnosis of human papillomavirus genital tract infection. The American Journal of Medicine. 1997;102(5):21-7
16. Og A, Oe O, To A. Sensitivity of a Papanicolaou smear in the diagnosis of candida albicans infection of the cervix. North American Journal of Medicine and Science. 2010;2(2):97-9
17. Alteras I and Aryeli J. The incidence of *Candida albicans* in the last day of pregnancy and the first days of the new born. Mycopathologia. 1980;72(2):85-7.
18. Oni AA1, Adu FD, Ekweozor CC, Bakare RA. Genital herpes simplex virus infection in females in Ibadan Nigeria. West African Journal of Medicine. 1996;15(2):107-10.
19. Tawfik O, Davis M, Dillon S, Tawfik L, Diaz FJ, FF. Whole slide imaging of Pap cell block preparations versus liquid-based thin-layer cervical cytology: a comparative study evaluating the detection of organisms and nonneoplastic findings. Acta cytologica. 2014;58(4):388-97.